

Studies in Organo-Fluorine Compounds : Part I. Synthesis of Some Substituted Glycines and Related Compounds of Potential Biological Activity

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Several fluorine containing Ethyl-N-2-thiazolyl glycines have been prepared and converted into glycyhydrazides. The latter have been condensed with various carbonyl compounds to yield substituted glycy hydrazones. These are expected to display interesting biological properties.

Various N-substituted glycines have been synthesised as potential tuberculostats¹. Finger *et al.*² have prepared N-phenylglycines as potential herbicides. It has been shown that hydrazides and hydrazones of various N-substituted glycines show antitubercular activity of high order^{3 4}. N-thiazolynicotinamide and isonicotinic hydrazide display marked anti-tubercular activity⁵.

In view of above observations and guided by the fact that a thiazole nucleus is present in many physiologically important natural products and that various types of chemotherapeutics, drugs and pesticides also contain this nucleus, it was anticipated that a combination of this heterocycle with amino acids would yield compounds of enhanced biological properties. Introduction of fluorine in such molecules would be advantageous in the sense that owing to its small atomic radius it may not materially affect the molecular size and still may modify their physiological characteristics. Based on these considerations the title compounds have been synthesised.

The required 2-amino-thiazoles were prepared according to the method of King and Hlavacek⁶ by heating thiourea with appropriate fluoroketones. These were condensed with ethyl chloroacetate in presence of sodium acetate to yield ethyl N-thiazolyl glycines¹. The latter were converted into hydrazides and hydrazones in usual way.

EXPERIMENTAL

m-Fluorotoluene was prepared by a modification of the Balz-Schiemann reaction⁷ from *m*-toluidine (40 g.) using sodium fluoborate in place of hydrofluoric acid. Yield 20 g. (48%), b.p. 114–15°. Literature⁷ records same b.p.

1. Vinay S. Misra and R. S. Varma, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 799.
2. G. C. Finger, *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8** (3), 405.
3. Ng. Ph. Buu-Hoi, *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1358.
4. Ng. Ph. Buu-Hoi and N. D. Xuong, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 186.
5. S. Kushner *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1948, **13**, 834.
6. Z. Carroll King and Robert J. Hlavacek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3722.
7. G. Balz and G. Schieman, *Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 1186; R. Adams, "Organic Reactions", Vol. V, pp. 203, 211.

p-Fluoroanisole was prepared according to the method of English *et al.*⁸ from *p*-anisidine (50 g.), yield 22.5 g. (45%), b.p. 158°. Adams *et al.*⁷ report b.p. 156–57°.

p-Fluorophenol was obtained by demethylation of *p*-fluoroanisole⁹.

2-Methyl-4-fluoroacetophenone was prepared by treating *m*-fluorotoluene (20 g.) with acetyl chloride (16 g.) and anhydrous AlCl₃ (32 g.) in CS₂ (75 ml.). Yield 12 g. (43.6%) b.p. 205–206°. Buu-Hoi and Xuong¹⁰ report same b.p.

2-Hydroxy-5-fluoroacetophenone was prepared by Fries rearrangement of 4-fluorophenylacetate¹¹.

2-Amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-fluoro)phenylthiazole: A mixture of 2-methyl-4-fluoroacetophenone (23 g.), thiourea (24 g.) and iodine (38 g.) was heated on a steam bath for 20 hr. The reaction mixture was treated with ether and subsequently with a solution of hypo. The gummy product was washed several times with water and then boiled with NH₄OH solution. The solid thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 129–30°, yield 18.8 g. (60%). Found: S, 15.21, Calc. for C₁₀H₉FN₂S; S, 15.38%.

2-Acetamido-4-(2'-methyl-4'-fluoro)phenylthiazole was obtained by following the procedure of Das and Rout¹². The thiazole compound (2 g.) obtained above was refluxed with acetic anhydride (20 ml.) for two hr; the mixture was poured into ice-water and the solid thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from absolute ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 212°, yield 2.2 g. (91%). Found: S, 12.21, Calc. for C₁₂H₁₁FN₂OS: S, 12.80%.

2-Amino-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluoro)phenylthiazole was prepared by above method from 2-hydroxy-5-fluoroacetophenone (15.4 g.), thiourea (15 g.) and iodine (25.4 g.) and the product isolated as usual, m.p. 155°, yield 10.9 g. (52%). Found: S, 15.52; Calc. for C₉H₇N₂OFS: S, 15.23%.

2-Acetamido-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluoro)phenylthiazole was prepared as usual from 2-amino-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluoro)phenylthiazole (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (15 ml.) as a colourless solid, m.p. 190°, yield 1.2 g. (66%). Found: S, 12.43; Calc. for C₁₁H₉N₂O₂FS: S, 12.69%.

Ethyl-N-{4-(2'-methyl-4'-fluorophenyl)thiazol-2-yl}glycinate: An intimate mixture of ethylchloroacetate (1M), 2-amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-fluoro)phenylthiazole (1M) and sodium acetate (2M) in ethanol (75%) was heated on steam bath for 4 hr. This was then poured into water. Upon cooling and adding a little dilute Na₂CO₃ solution, a brownish precipitate was obtained. This was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. M.P. 120–22°, yield (48%). Found: S, 11.23; Calc. for C₁₄H₁₅N₂O₂FS: S, 10.88%.

N-4-{{2'-Methyl-4'-fluorophenyl}thiazol-2-yl}glycylhydrazide: Upon treating above glycinate (1M) with hydrazine hydrate (2M, 95%) in usual way, the acid hydrazide was obtained as a dark brown solid, m.p. 125–26°, yield (66%). Found: S, 11.63; Calc. for C₁₂H₁₃N₄OFS: S, 11.42%.

8. James English Jr., J. F. Mead and Carl Niemann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 350.

9. K. C. Joshi and S. Giri, *This Journal*, 1961, **33**, 117.

10. Ng. Ph. Buu-Hoi and Ng. D. Xuong, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 386.

11. K. C. Joshi and S. Giri, *This Journal*, 1962, **39**, 185.

12. K. C. Das and M. K. Rout, *ibid.*, 1955, **32**, 663.

Ethyl-N-{4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluorophenyl) thiazol-2-yl}-glycinate was prepared by above procedure by reacting together equimolar quantities of 2-amino-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluorophenyl) thiazole and ethyl chloroacetate, m.p. 194°. yield (45%). Found : S, 10.97; Calc. for $C_{13}H_{13}N_2O_3FS$: S, 10.81%.

N-{4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluorophenyl) thiazol-2-yl}-glycylhydrazide : M.P. 161°, yield (64%). Found : S, 11.15; Calc. for $C_{11}H_{11}N_4O_2FS$: S, 11.36%.

N-2-(Substituted thiazolyl) glycyl hydrazones : The appropriate glycyl hydrazide (1M) in absolute ethanol was refluxed with requisite aldehyde or ketone (1M) dissolved in the same solvent. The reaction with aldehydes was complete in about an hour while with ketones it took four to five hours. The products were isolated as usual.

The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	R ₁	R ₂	M.P.	% Yield	Formula	% Sulphur	
						Found	Required
Ar = 2-Methyl-4-fluorophenyl-							
1.	H	4-hydroxy-P*	112°	75	$C_{19}H_{17}N_4O_2FS$	8.43	8.33
2.	H	2-hydroxy-P	115-16°	66	$C_{19}H_{17}N_4O_2FS$	8.02	8.33
3.	H	4-methoxy-P	123°	62	$C_{20}H_{19}N_4O_2FS$	8.43	8.04
4.	H	phenyl	128°	65	$C_{19}H_{17}N_4OFS$	8.44	8.69
5.	CH ₃	methyl	135-36°	60	$C_{15}H_{17}N_4OFS$	10.27	10.00
Ar = 2-Hydroxy-5-fluorophenyl-							
6.	H	4-hydroxy-P	165°	68	$C_{18}H_{15}N_4O_3FS$	8.16	8.28
7.	H	4-methoxy-P	135°	66	$C_{19}H_{17}N_4O_3FS$	8.23	8.00
8.	H	styryl	140°	62	$C_{20}H_{17}N_4O_2FS$	8.35	8.08
9.	CH ₃	ethyl	155°	60	$C_{15}H_{17}N_4O_2FS$	9.29	9.52
10.	C ₂ H ₅	ethyl	164°	61	$C_{16}H_{19}N_4O_2FS$	9.20	9.42
11.	C ₆ H ₅	methyl	158°	65	$C_{19}H_{17}N_4O_2FS$	8.52	8.33

* P denotes phenyl.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Head, Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur for providing all necessary facilities. One of us (A. Mahmood) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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Received August 21, 1968.